

**TYPES OF RHEOLOGICAL MATRIXES IN CONCRETE MIXTURE,
MEDIUM-SIZED TERRAIN STRATEGY FOR INCREASING THE STRENGTH
OF CONCRETE AND SAVING IT IN STRUCTURES.**

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Annotation: *Portland cement savings strategy, structures made of concrete of such grades, design of products and structures made of high-strength concrete, as well as existing production technologies.*

Key words: *concrete, cement-water, Superplasticizers, matrices, components - cement, crushed stone, sand, superplasticizer, water reaches.*

The most radical revolutionary stage on the long path of the evolutionary development of concrete was the emergence of effective super plasticizers (SP) and hyper plasticizers (HP) of a new generation. The creation of high-strength concretes with super plasticizers was carried out in several directions related to the creation of highly fluid fine-dispersed rheological matrices.

At the first stage, the basis of self-spreading and self-compacting concrete mixtures was a cement-water dispersion. Naturally, in "lean" concretes of low grades M 100-300 with low cement consumption, the effectiveness of super plasticizers was very low, since the volume of the rheological matrix from the cement-water dispersion was insignificant.

Superplasticizers began to be used more effectively in concrete grades 400-500 with cement consumption of 500-600 kg/m³. Due to a more significant water-reducing effect and a decrease in the amount of water, it became possible to reduce the cost of cement by 10-20% in the production of reinforced concrete pressure pipes, beams, trusses, columns, providing the same strength of 40-50 MPa with non-additive concretes on equally mobile mixtures.

In this case, too, the cement was saved by reducing the volume of the rheological matrix, but denser, forming high strength.

The strategy for saving Portland cement in Uzbekistan and in the CIS countries, with the use of joint ventures from 1979 to the present, has not turned into the most rational, promising radical strategy for saving concrete in load-bearing structures and products through the use of high-strength concrete grades 1400-2000 in them.

The enormous technical and economic efficiency of such concretes in the future is obvious. In structures made of concrete of such grades, with its rise in price by 1.4-1.7 times, the reduction in the consumption of all components - cement, crushed stone, sand, super plasticizer and water reaches 2-4 times! not counting savings in fittings when switching to high grade steel.

And this is a colossal reduction in the mass of buildings and structures and a concomitant reduction in transport costs. Is it possible to talk about reducing the consumption of cement in a cube of concrete grades 500-600 by only 80-100 kg with such huge savings? Is it not worth changing the entire technical policy in the field of designing products and structures made of high-strength concrete, as well as existing technologies for their production with all available.

A park of molds of huge capacity and metal consumption. But which of the production workers will decide to make a reinforced concrete lintel of an I-beam or box-shaped section from concrete grade M1500 or more, a hollow foundation of complex shape in accordance with the diagrams of the main stresses of the Column with a 3-fold decrease in the section, but with the preservation of the moment of resistance and the moment of inertia of the section?

Conservatism in the restructuring of thinking and designers and technologists does not allow Russia to make a revolutionary leap in the production of high-strength concrete. And this means constantly lagging behind the advanced countries in the economy of reinforced concrete construction. Isn't it easier for manufacturers and builders to get their own, although small profits, on the "old" four-component concrete, which is almost 160 years old.

Foreign experience shows that high-strength and extra-high-strength concretes of grades M1400 and more are in demand in the construction of special, especially loaded structures, such as large-span bridges, skyscrapers, offshore oil platforms, tanks for storing gases and liquids under pressure, and other structures.

Significant progress in this has been especially noted since the late 80s of the last century, when high-strength concretes with joint ventures were produced with high cement consumption. Modern high-quality concretes (HKB) classify a wide range of concretes for various purposes: high-strength and ultra-high-strength concretes [1, 2], self-compacting concretes [3, 4], and highly corrosion-resistant concretes.

These types of concrete, reinforced with bar and dispersed reinforcement or a combination of them, meet the high requirements for compressive and tensile strength, crack resistance, impact strength, wear resistance, corrosion resistance, and frost resistance.

Of course, the transition to new types of concrete was facilitated, firstly, not only by revolutionary achievements in the field of plasticizing concrete and mortar mixtures, but, secondly, by the emergence of the most active pozzolanic additives - silica fume (MF), dehydrated kaolins and highly dispersed reactive ash. CHP plants are denser than natural, highly porous pozzolans.

The combination of superplasticizers and, especially, environmentally friendly hyperplasticizers based on polycarboxylate, polyacrylate, and polyglycol bases make it possible to obtain superfluid cement-mineral dispersed systems and concrete mixes. Thanks to these achievements, the number of components in concrete with chemical additives has reached 6-8, the water-cement ratio has decreased to 0.24-0.28, while maintaining plasticity, characterized by a cone draft of 4-10 cm.

In self-compacting concretes (Selbstverdichtender Beton-SVB) with or without the addition of stone flour (KM), but with the addition of MK in high-performance concretes (Ultrahochfester Beton, Ultra hochleistung Beton) on hyper plasticizers, in contrast to those cast on traditional joint ventures, perfect fluidity of concrete mixtures is combined with low sedimentation and self-compacting with spontaneous removal of air.

"High" rheology with a significant water reduction in super plasticized concrete mixtures is provided by a fluid rheological matrix, which can be divided in high-strength concretes into several scale levels according to the size of the structural elements that make it up.

In ordinary crushed stone concretes of low grades for crushed stone, a cement-sand mortar serves as a rheological matrix at a complex structural level, namely at the meso-micro level. In turn, for sand in conventional concrete mixes, the rheological matrix at the micro level is a cement-water paste, the proportion of which can be increased to ensure fluidity by increasing the amount of cement.

But this, on the one hand, is uneconomical (especially for concretes of classes B10-B30), on the other hand, paradoxically, all the strongest superplasticizers are "bad" water-reducing additives for Portland cement, although they were all created and are being created for it.

Cement is an unstable in water, hydrating system that forms supercolloidal particles immediately after its contact with water and quickly thickens. And colloidal particles and gels in water are difficult to disperse with super plasticizers. An example is clay slurries that are difficult to super fluidize. Particles of a number of rocks, even the thinnest, do not change in water for hundreds and thousands of years.

So, in highly plasticized concrete mixtures for high-strength concretes for crushed stone, as a macrostructural element, the rheological matrix is a more complex dispersion consisting of sand, cement, stone flour, microsilica and water.

The proportion of such a matrix should be significantly higher than in conventional concretes.

This leads to the conclusion: stone flour should be added to the cement and it will increase not only the rheological effect of the joint venture on the mixture, but also, not more importantly, the volume of the rheological matrix itself. As a result, it becomes possible to more significantly reduce the amount of water than in the cement-water matrix, increase the density and increase the strength of concrete.

And the addition of stone flour, in practice, will be tantamount to an increase in cement, if the water-reducing effects are much higher than with the addition of cement.

It is important here to focus not on replacing part of the cement with stone flour, as previously recommended, when using joint venture, but adding it in a significant amount - up to 40-60% to Portland cement.

Based on the polystructural theory in 1985-2000. all work on changing the polys structure was aimed at replacing 30-40% of Portland cement with mineral fillers to save it in concrete grades M200-500 Let's compare two identical concrete compositions by weight of dry components, but with different amounts of finely dispersed components for a microlevel rheological matrix. In the first six-component composition (taking into account

water and joint venture) 40% of cement was replaced by stone flour (CM): C=300 kg; KM - 200 kg; P=575 kg; W = 1300 kg. In the second composition, 50% of stone flour was added to the cement: C = 500 kg; KM = 250 kg; W = 1050 kg, and the sand content is the same. Let us compare the volumes of finely dispersed components at $\rho_c = 3.1 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $\rho_{km} = 2.7 \text{ g/cm}^3$. In the first case, it will be 170.2 liters, and in the second, 253.7 liters, i.e. 50% higher. Thus, in the first composition of the CM, acting as a cement filler, it does not increase the volume of the rheological water-dispersed component.

In high-strength concretes with microsilica for a mixture of cement and stone flour as structural elements, there must be another rheological matrix with a nanoscale level - a mixture of silica fume, water and superplasticizer. Microsilica particle sizes are usually in the range of 0.1-1.0 μm , i.e. to the top level of nanoparticles.

As part of a seven-component high-strength concrete with microsilica class B70-B80: C = 500 kg; KM = 250 kg, MK = 75 kg; P = 500 kg W = 1050 kg at $\rho_{mk} = 2.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$ the volume of the dispersed component of the nanomicro level is 287 liters. those. 68.5% higher. than in the first concrete with a strength of 40-50 MPa. Microsilica, in addition to the structural-topological function in the rheological matrix, performs a reaction-chemical one.

And it must be added 10-20% by weight of Portland cement to bind all the hydrolytic lime that is inevitably present in concrete. And the largest amount of it is released by alite ($3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$). If we focus on the formation of hydrosilicates with a basicity of 1.5 during the hydrolysis of alite according to the reaction $2(3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2)+6\text{H}_2\text{O} = 3\text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{SiO}_2\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}+3\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, then the amount of released portlandite will be 39.36%.

When using normal Portland cement with alite content

60%, the amount of formed portlandite will be 23.6%. When the content of belite ($\beta\text{-}2\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$) in cement is up to 20% and its hydrolysis according to the reaction portlandite will be 27.7%.

Thus, the proportion of microsilica in cement (with its complete hydration) should be at least 22% of its mass, based on the stoichiometric ratio $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2:\text{SiO}_2$, equal to 1.23:1 for

The maximum rheological and water-reducing effects due to the adsorption of SP on the surface of the solid phase are “genetically” characteristic of finely dispersed systems with a high interface.

From Table. 1 it can be seen that in Portland cement casting slurries with joint venture, the water-reducing effect (Vd) of the latter is 1.5-7.0 times lower than in mineral powders. For rocks, the dewatering can be 2-3 times higher than in cement.

table

Rheological and water-reducing action of SP in water-mineral systems

Type of dispersed powder and plasticizer	Dosage SP, %	Pd	Vd
CaCO_3 (M 150)	1,0	360-400	3,2-3,5

BaCO ₃ (Melment)	1,0	1800-2000	5,0-6,0
Cr ₂ O ₃ (C-3)	1,5	1200-1500	2,7-3,0
Ca(OH) ₂ (JICT)	0,4	5000-6000	8,0-8,5
ZnO (C-3)	1,5	7000-7500	12,0-14,0
CaCO ₃ (M 150)	1,0	360-400	3,2-3,5
Cement PO "Volskement" (C-3)	1,0	30-35	1,8-2,0
Opoka Penza field	2,0	10-12	1,1-1,2
Ground glass TF10	1,0	14-18	1,5-1,6
Dolomite natural (SMF)	1,0	400-500	2,8-3,0
	0,9	1400-1600	4,2-4,6

The combination of hyperplasticizers with microsilica, stone flour or ash made it possible to raise the level of compressive strength to 130-150, and in some cases up to 180-200 MPa or more. However, a significant increase in strength leads to an intensive increase in brittleness and a decrease in Poisson's ratio to 0.14-0.17, which leads to the risk of sudden brittle fracture of structures in emergency situations. Getting rid of this negative property of concrete is carried out not only by reinforcing the latter with rod reinforcement, but also by combining rod reinforcement with the introduction of fibers from polymers, glass and steel.

Energy and energy saving.

Enormous energy savings during the transition to the production of high-strength concrete in all related industries have been discussed above.

The technology of production of PC is highly energy-consuming, associated with its firing at a high temperature (1450-1500 ° C), crushing and grinding of raw materials and clinker (in the production of cement, 70-80% of all electricity is spent on crushing, grinding). This direction directly relates to the improvement of the environment by reducing emissions of exhaust gases from the combustion of organic fuels and the release of heat into the atmosphere.

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